

Coils and helical windings as polarization controllers

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ABSTRACT:

Fiber coils have a wide application in fiber optics, since the necessity of compact fiber devices has been solved winding the fibers. However, coiled fibers show regularly a stress induced birefringence which needs to be taken into account. In general, it is only when two or three coils are combined that their polarization effects are not only considered relevant, but are used to control the state of polarization of light. These devices, known as polarization controllers, rely on the birefringence properties of the fiber coils and their relative orientation. The polarization performance of a three-ring polarization controller has been described assuming that the coil of each ring behaves as a quarter- or half-wave retarder [1]. This is a clear and useful approximation when the signal is monochromatic, but the verification of this assumption is not easy to accomplish.

In this work we verify the similar performance of polarization controllers built with two helical coils and with three non-regular windings, applying them to the cancellation of the effect of birefringence on the output state of polarization of a signal. We verify that states of polarization entering and leaving the controller can be equal using either option.

Key words: optical fiber; birefringence; polarization

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1. Introduction

The necessity of compact fiber devices has been solved in practice using fiber coils. Nevertheless it is important to realize that when a fiber is coiled, its residual birefringence is modified. In general, it is only when two or three coils are combined that their polarization effects are considered relevant by the user. These devices, known as polarization

controllers (Fig. 1), rely on the birefringence properties of the fiber coils and their relative orientation. It should be noticed that even when only one fiber winding is used, strain-induced birefringence modifies the residual birefringence of the fiber and consequently the polarization performance of the fiber device. Comparing the polarization models reported in the literature for a helical fiber coil, we found there is no agreement on the descriptions presented by different authors. Since we consider it is important to understand these changes in order to build better fiber systems and devices, making use of the geometrical properties of a helix, we developed a birefringence model for a fiber helical coil. This matrix model includes the strain-induced birefringence of the helical coil (bend- and twist-induced) and the geometrical contribution due to its out-of-plane trajectory. Using the birefringence matrix model of one helical coil, we investigated the description of a polarization controller formed by two helical coils, taking into account the modification of the relative orientation of the separate fiber windings. We present an experimental comparison of polarization controllers formed by two helical coils and common polarization controllers using three non-regular coils, applying them to the cancellation of the effect of birefringence on the output state of polarization of a signal.

Fig. 1. Polarization controllers with three and two fiber rings.

2. Helical Fiber Structures

2.a.- Birefringence modification induced by helical windings

Making use of the geometrical properties of a helix, it has been recently shown [2] that a helical fiber coil, due to the residual elliptical birefringence of the uncoiled fiber (straight fiber), has linear and circular birefringence components. In addition, due to the helical winding, an additional linear birefringence (induced by bending) and a modification in the linear and circular components of the residual birefringence (produced by torsion) are observed [3]. Furthermore, since a helix is an out-of-plane curve, there is also a geometric rotation [4]. These results are important and explain why the comparison of the polarization models reported in the literature for a helical fiber show no agreement regarding their descriptions (references 4-22 in [2]).

Despite of all the phenomena involved, the resultant model is simple. It is equal to the product of a gyration matrix by an elliptical retarder matrix \mathbf{M}_r with a twist dependence [2]

$$\mathbf{R}(\zeta + b\tau)\mathbf{M}_r, \quad (1)$$

i.e., due to torsion, the retardation angle δ_0 between the polarization eigenmodes of the straight fiber is modified by a term that varies linearly with torsion τ ($\delta = \delta_0 + c\tau$, c is a constant), and the term $b\tau$ reflects the geometrical rotation of the fast birefringence axis (b is a constant) [3]; the gyration angle ζ is equal to $n2\pi(1 - \cos\xi)$, being n the number of helix loops [4].

2.b.- Polarization controller formed by two helical coils

Two consecutive helical coils formed with fibers with equal length, radius and pitch length, but opposite handedness, allow the cancelation of the effect of birefringence on the state of polarization of the output signal (the

input and output polarization states are equal) [5]. For completeness, the theoretical justification of this result is repeated below.

Applying the matrix model of Eq. (1) to the structure of two helical coils

$$\mathbf{M}_{2H} = \mathbf{R}(-\theta)\mathbf{R}(\zeta + b\tau)\mathbf{M}_r\mathbf{R}(\theta)\mathbf{R}(-\vartheta)\mathbf{R}(-\zeta - b\tau)\mathbf{M}_{-r}\mathbf{R}(\vartheta), \quad (2)$$

where angles θ and ϑ are the azimuth angles of the fast birefringence axis of each helical coil; i.e., indicate the orientation of the fast birefringence axis of each helical coil with respect to the laboratory reference frame. When the relative orientation of the helical coils is modified until the relation

$$\mathbf{R}(\theta)\mathbf{R}(-\vartheta)\mathbf{R}(-\zeta - b\tau) = \mathbf{1} \quad (3)$$

is satisfied; since $\mathbf{M}_r\mathbf{M}_{-r} = \mathbf{1}$ and using (3) we have that $\mathbf{R}(-\theta)\mathbf{R}(\zeta + b\tau)\mathbf{R}(\vartheta) = \mathbf{1}$, we can observe that the result of equation (2) is the identity matrix $\mathbf{1}$.

3. Birefringence induced by an irregular winding

In this case we have no information on the specific retardation introduced by each fiber coil. Hence, as implied in [1] it would be necessary to measure the birefringence contribution of the coiled fiber in each ring to be able to understand how the cancellation of the effect of the polarizer controller birefringence on the state of polarization of the output signal takes place.

We should mention that despite the lack of a non-empiric model for a non-regularly wound fiber, in practice, both polarization controllers (PC) present a similar performance.

4. Polarization control using regular and irregular windings

Experimental results for the two types of polarization controllers were obtained using the optical set up shown in figure 2. The laser source was a tunable laser diode HP8168C with an isolator at the output to protect it from reflected light. A polarization controller was used to produce a circular state of polarization at the prism polarizer input for each signal wavelength. The prism polarizer was used to generate the linear polarizations used to create the laboratory reference frame in the polarization analyzer Agilent 8509C (removing the part of the set up within the marked rectangle) and the linear input signals used to characterize the polarization performance of the polarization controller under study. Air-fiber couplers were oriented to collimate light coming from the fiber, or to focus it to be injected into the fiber core.

Both polarization controllers were fabricated with standard single mode fiber SMF-28e. The fiber length was ~ 2 m for the three-ring polarization controller and one third of this length was used to build each coil. To minimize bend-induced attenuation we used coils with ~ 5 cm in diameter. For helical coils we have used several fiber lengths from ~ 1 to 4 m. In this case, to minimize twist-induced birefringence changes we used a minimum pitch (fiber loops were in contact, [5,6]).

Fig. 2. Optical arrangement used to perform the cancellation of the effect of birefringence on the output signal.

For the cancellation procedure we followed the process described by Rodriguez Garcia [6]. A circularly polarized signal was launched at the polarization controller input end and the relative orientation of the fiber coils was modified until the state of polarization of the output signal was equal to the input SOP. Then, using the same signal wavelength, the prism polarizer was inserted, its azimuth angle was rotated from 0 to 360° and the output states of polarization were mapped on a Poincaré sphere. The trajectory was located very close to the equator, as we can see in figure 3 (the signal wavelength was 1555 nm), indicating that a linear input SOP remains almost linear at the output.

The results obtained for two helical windings are very similar, as we can see in references [5] and [6], for any signal wavelength within the 1520 to 1570 nm band.

Fig 3. Trajectory depicted by the output polarization state of a 1555 nm input signal when the linear polarization state varied from 0 to 360°.

The deviation of the depicted major circles from the sphere equator indicates the amount of unwanted circular birefringence contribution. This deviation can be quantified using the maximum and minimum values reached by the ellipticity angle. For all the wavelengths investigated in this work (1520 to 1570 nm, with a 5 nm step) their absolute values were smaller than 7°. We should mention that for the three-ring polarization controller the symmetry in the variation of the ellipticity angle was slightly poorer. For any given signal wavelength, we obtained variations between the maximum and minimum ellipticity angles up to ~2°, while this value was much smaller than 1° for a

system formed by two helical coils. These results showed only small variations of the maximum or minimum ellipticity angles (smaller than 2°) within the 10 h time interval we monitored the stability of the output polarization states.

5. Conclusions

The polarization control achieved by a polarization controller built with two helical coils of standard fiber is very similar to that achieved by a three-ring polarization controller built with non-regularly wound fiber coils for fiber lengths of ~ 2 to 3 m.

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